

SpikeInterface-GUI: efficient and versatile spike sorting visualization and curation

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Abstract

Extracellular electrophysiology is a key technique in neuroscience, but the scale and diversity of the produced data make it difficult to visualize. Additionally the rapid development of new spike sorting algorithms creates a significant challenge for researchers trying to assess and compare these tools. In this paper we introduce **SpikeInterface-GUI**, a flexible visualization tool tightly integrated with **SpikeInterface**, designed to display raw ephys data and information about spike sorted units. Researchers can utilize the GUI to curate output by labeling, merging and splitting units, and use a plugin system to create their own bespoke data visualizations. There are two backends, including a web-based backend designed to support deployment on a web-server or centralized workstation. When set up, this allows global collaborations to easily share and compare results on a web browser without having to install any software.

Introduction

Extracellular electrophysiology is one of the most popular techniques in neuroscience to readout neural activity at single-cell resolution. Recordings are taken from a diverse range of devices: single electrodes and tetrodes with a few channels, high-density needle-like shanks with tens to hundreds of channels [1, 2, 3], and *in vitro* systems with thousands of channels which produce terabyte-scale data [4]. Regardless of the device used, spike sorting is an essential computational step which takes the raw recordings as input and returns a list of spikes from individual putative neurons (or *units*) [5]. Different types of recordings and data can be processed in different ways, e.g., different spike sorting algorithms and processing step are used for low versus high-density probe data. The size of modern data, the combination of diverse formats and algorithms, and the global-scale international collaboration common to neuroscience means that it is more difficult for researchers to visualize and distill their data and results than ever before.

Just as physical technology has evolved, so has algorithmic development in the field. As well as new spike sorters [6, 7, 8, 9], there are new motion correction [10, 11], auto-curation [12, 13], auto-merging [14, 15] and unit-matching [16, 17] tools. For a researcher to make informed decisions about algorithm choice, it is essential that they can visualize these outputs clearly, even when their data set is large. They also need to be able to test and compare different algorithms. To aid this task, **SpikeInterface** [18] has recently added new tools to standardize the post-processing of spike sorted data, no matter the input data-type or sorting algorithm used. In version 0.101 of **SpikeInterface**, released in July 2024, the **SortingAnalyzer** was added. This object represents a combined recording and sorting, and computes “extensions” from this data such as: unit locations, correlograms, principal components, quality metrics, and the spike-amplitude and -depth distributions. The results are saved in a simple standardized format, which other tools can use as a starting point to build upon.

In version 0.103 of **SpikeInterface** a **Curation** format was added, implemented as a **Pydantic** model [19], which allows a user (or algorithm) to prescribe labels, merges, and splits

for spike sorted units. The envisioned workflow is for the user to create a **SortingAnalyzer** from spike sorted output, compute information about the putative units, use this information to compute (or to manually create) a **Curation**, then apply the **Curation** to create a curated analyzer. This workflow retains the original analyzer and the curation decisions made by the user, hence preserving provenance and allowing for reproducible curation. In practice, users are able to check, modify, undo and try different automated curation algorithms applied to the same analyzer. For this workflow to be effective, a user must be able to easily visualize the spike sorting output alongside the curation decisions.

Currently, two open source GUIs exist to view and curate spike sorting output. **SortingView** [20] is a web-based tool that allows users to easily share the results of their spike sorting, and is based on the **SortingAnalyzer** from **SpikeInterface**. However, it lacks the ability to compute further information and has no ability to access raw data traces. **Phy** [21] is a popular desktop-based application which supports visualization and curation of sorting output from **KiloSort**, **SpykingCircus** and **Klusta**. However, it has seen sporadic updates since its latest stable release in November 2016. Several beta releases were made between February 2020 and September 2021, then there were no updates until a new release candidate was announced in March 2026.

In this paper, we introduce **SpikeInterface-GUI**, a visualization tool for spike sorter output from **SpikeInterface**, including curation decisions. When run, the user can see an overview of each putative unit from a spike sorting output, including its template (average waveform), spike-amplitude and -depth distribution, a principal component projection, its location on a probe, and more. Curation decisions, such as quality labels and units which should be merged, can also be viewed and a user can either accept or reject the suggestions. The curation can either be created in **SpikeInterface** before the user launches the GUI, or several auto-merging algorithms are embedded in the GUI. Users can view raw data, preprocessed in various ways. The raw data are handled by **SpikeInterface**, which in turn relies on **python-Neo** [22] for file-format specific readers. Over 30 recording formats are supported, and this implementation allows for “lazy loading”, so that the recording is not loaded into the computer’s memory. This means that the GUI supports visualization of terabyte-scale recordings even on an average laptop. Individual spikes can also be superimposed on the raw data, enabling spike-level inspection of the spike sorting results.

The **SpikeInterface-GUI** is designed with flexibility in mind. It comes with a desktop backend (implemented in **QT** [23]/**PyQtGraph** [24]) for local, single-user, efficient deployment. In addition, there is a web-based version (implemented with **Panel** [25]) designed for collaborative shared deployments on centralized workstations or in the cloud.

Design and Implementation

SpikeInterface-GUI is tightly integrated with **SpikeInterface**, a popular Python package for spike sorting, which wraps many different sorters and algorithms. The basic **SpikeInterface** pipeline is: read in an electrophysiological recording (around 30 formats are supported), apply preprocessing including motion correction as necessary, run any supported spike sorter, and then compute features of the sorting such as the waveforms, templates, principal components, and spike distributions. There is extensive documentation and courses available that teach users how to create this type of analysis pipeline. The final output of the pipeline is a **SortingAnalyzer** (referred to as *analyzer*), and **SpikeInterface-GUI** uses the analyzer as its basic input object. The analyzer introduced a unified format to store both the recording and sorting output from many sorters. By linking to the recording data rather than copying it, the analyzer remains lightweight while providing a standardized base object which can be used to compare sorters and develop new tools on top of. The analyzer output has a simple form – data is stored in a “binary” format (folder-based, using **.npy** or **.csv** for data files and **JSON** for metadata) or a “zarr” format [26]. Other tools such as **SortingView** [20], **UnitRefine** [13] and **NeuroConv** [27] already use the analyzer as a starting point. **SpikeInterface** supports exporting an analyzer to other formats such as **Pynapple** [28] and **Phy** (and importing and wrangling other formats such as **Phy** input into an analyzer).

To use **SpikeInterface-GUI** a user can first open the launcher, a small GUI which allows them to select an analyzer from their filesystem to inspect and adjust some settings, such as

the layout. For more control, users can input these choices through a command line interface or by writing a Python script to launch the main `SpikeInterface-GUI` window. When this window is opened, `SpikeInterface-GUI` loads the chosen analyzer and re-organizes the data to optimize for fast retrieval. The reorganized data is stored in a Controller, which also handles signaling across the GUI.

A `SpikeInterface-GUI` window is constructed from a selection of Views. Each View displays information about one or more of the spike sorted units. Depending on their use case, a user may specify a different selection of Views to include in their window, and fine-tune their plotting settings as desired. There are currently twenty-one Views implemented. Examples of fully functional `SpikeInterface-GUI` windows made from numerous Views are discussed later in the text, and are shown in Figures 2, 3, 4 and 5.

The codebase has been designed so that developers can easily add new Views. The code for each View is contained in a single Python file that describes how to retrieve the required data from the Controller and how to plot it. A simple View, such as ‘IsiView’ is implemented in less than 200 lines of code. Since a View is self-contained in one file with no cross-dependencies with the others, the codebase can be easily maintained and extended. We have also implemented a plugin system so that users can add custom Views for their bespoke experiment. An example of a custom View is described later in the text, and can be seen in Figure 5.

Each View has two visual backends: we use `Qt` for a desktop application and `Panel` as the basis for a web-based viewer. The visualization is decoupled from the data handling of the Controller. The desktop application is designed for a traditional deployment: a single user runs it on their computer, viewing and curating local (or streamed) data. The `Panel` web application allows for deployment on a centralized workstation or a web server, allowing users from anywhere in the world to access the application on their web browsers without having to install any software. Further, the `SortingAnalyzer` can be loaded from an s3 bucket rather than a local folder. This web-first setup allows for large-scale global collaborations to store their data in the cloud and visualize it using the GUI. The different deployment methodologies

Figure 1: Two ways to deploy `SpikeInterface-GUI`. A desktop deployment, based on our PyQT backend, is suitable for a single user in a lab. A web-based deployment, based on our `Panel` backend, allows user from different labs to access cloud-stored data through the GUI on a web browser. Users do not need to install any software to view the GUI and curation decisions could be saved to an external database. This is an example deployment – users could also use the `Panel` backend in a more traditional way to load local data and save their decisions to a JSON file.

are schematized in Figure 1.

A web-based system is deployed at the Allen Institute for Neural Dynamics (ephys.allenneuraldynamics.org) to centralize access, visualization, and curation of spike sorting results. To support a smooth and flexible integration of spike sorting curation in various workflows, the `SpikeInterface-GUI` can be given a `curation_callback` method, which enables developers to customize the spike sorting curation saving procedure. For example, one can decide to save the curation JSON file to a specific location, e.g., `session_path/curation.json`, or even to save the curation data to a custom database, as is done at Allen.

As well as visualizing sorting output, `SpikeInterface-GUI` is designed to assess and compute curations. There are three possible curation steps: labeling a unit based on e.g. its quality or possible cell type, merging two units which have been *oversplit* by a spike sorting algorithm, and splitting one unit into two units which have been *overmerged* by a spike sorting algorithm. Users can either load a set of curation decisions which have been generated by an external algorithm, use the GUI to manually input curation decisions, or apply an algorithm within the GUI to generate decisions. Several algorithms have been ported and implemented in `SpikeInterface`, such as `SLAY` [15] and parts of `LUSSAC` [14]. We store the curation decisions internally as a Pydantic model called a `Curation`, and the user can export these as a human-readable JSON file or save them inside the analyzer. Because we save the decisions, a full provenance of the curation is kept. This improves reproducibility, and allows the user to subsequently undo decisions.

We recommend that users use a functional curation workflow. That is to generate, or manually create, a curation for the entire analyzer. Then tweak this curation by e.g. manually adjusting some decisions, or adjusting hyperparameters of an algorithm to create a new curation for the entire analyzer. Once the user is happy with the full curation, apply it to the entire analyzer to create a new, curated analyzer. Only at this stage is all information, such as templates and spike amplitudes re-computed.

As well as visualization, `SpikeInterface-GUI` can also perform computations. These include finding potential unit merges and re-computing data with new parameters, such as correlograms. All calculations are implemented in `SpikeInterface` and the GUI simply interfaces with these implementations.

Results

To demonstrate the utility of the GUI, we will describe how it can be used in four different scenarios. For each use case, we will create a custom layout, constructed of different Views. A user can use their own custom layouts by creating a layout JSON file, as described in the Documentation of `SpikeInterface-GUI`.

Quality curation involves looking at properties of a spike sorted unit and using these to determine an appropriate label for that unit. Commonly, labs label units as noise (signal arising from non-neuronal electrical activity), good (signal arising from a single neuron) and MUA (multi-unit activity, arising from a mixture of several neurons). Visual information that aids this decision include the spatial shape of the unit’s template, its auto-correlogram, the distribution of spike amplitudes and locations, and some quality metrics such as the signal to noise ratio. We display an instance of the web version of `SpikeInterface-GUI` showing some of these properties in Figure 2. On viewing this data, the user can label the displayed unit as “noise”, “good” or “MUA” by typing `n`, `g` or `m` on their keyboard. A user can also input their own labels or metrics. In the Figure, a list of brain regions has been passed to the GUI by the user.

Instead of doing manual curation, a user might use an external algorithm, such as `BombCell` [12], `UnitRefine` [13] or simple quality-metric based thresholding, to label units automatically, or to evaluate the performance of multiple auto-labeling tools. If they do so, they can then feed these labels into `SpikeInterface-GUI` to check the results of the algorithm. The visualization provided by the GUI is essential for users to feel confident using these automated tools, and can provide the feedback needed to adjust algorithmic hyperparameters.

`SpikeInterface-GUI` can be used to assess the results of a spike sorting. If the recording is available, this can be done at the level of individual spikes. The user can select any number

Figure 2: An example SpikeInterface-GUI window using the Panel web-based backend, showing Views with an emphasis on quality curation. A list of units is displayed alongside some metrics and a user defined `brain_area` label (top left). We also show the spike-amplitude distribution (bottom left), unit template (middle), auto-correlogram (top right) and spike rate (bottom right).

Figure 3: An example SpikeInterface-GUI window, with an emphasis on sorting output with raw data. We have selected two nearby units with different templates (yellow, green). The list of all spikes of both units is displayed in the bottom left. A spike has been selected and its waveform is superimposed on the templates (white line), demonstrating that the spike waveform is similar to its unit template. The traces are shown in two different ways: the traces from channels near the unit location is plotted as lines (top right) and the traces from all channels is rendered as a heat map (bottom right). In each trace view, the spike location is plotted.

of units and generate a list of their spikes. When an individual spike is selected, its spatial-temporal location is plotted on the raw trace and its raw waveform is computed in real time. This spike waveform can be overlaid on the unit template. In this way, the user can better understand why the spike has been clustered into a given unit, rather than another unit. In Figure 3 we plot such a scenario, where two units with differing templates have been selected and plotted alongside a spike from one of the units. The spike clearly matches the template of the unit it has been clustered into, as expected. This layout can also be used for pedagogical purposes, as it helps the viewer understand the link between spike sorting outputs and the raw data itself. Another use case of this view is to look at the spikes from noisy units. Often these come from artifacts in the recording, which the user can track down by scanning through the spikes from noisy units.

A common problem in spike sorting is over-splitting. This occurs when spikes from a single neuron are clustered into two or more units instead of one. Such units should be merged into a single unit post-sorting. In **SpikeInterface-GUI** the user can use similarity measures or test auto-merging algorithms directly to view potential merges. One can then use information such as the similarity of the templates, cross-correlograms between units and time distribution of their firing to decide if a merge is acceptable or not. Alternatively, the user could use **SpikeInterface-GUI** to view the proposed merges then adjust the parameters of the algorithm until they are happy to accept all automatically generated results. Figure 4 displays a **SpikeInterface-GUI** layout designed for making merge decisions. Different auto-merging algorithms can be selected at the top of the merging View. The user can scan through the putative merges and “accept” them by pressing **ctrl + A**. After all decisions have been made, the user can export a JSON file containing the decision using the export button in the curation view.

Spike sorters can also overmerge units, where two distinct units are merged into one. In

Figure 4: An example **SpikeInterface-GUI** window showing Views with an emphasis on merges. Here the user has run the SLAY auto-merge algorithm [15] and is comparing a pair of units that the algorithm has suggested to merge. The list of potential merges is displayed, as well as a collection of adjustable algorithm settings. We plot the spike amplitude distribution, templates, correlograms and spike rates of both units. In addition we plot a projection of their PCA components and two of their metrics (bottom right). The metric plot shows the distribution of metrics across all units, and where each of the two units lie on this distribution. Agreed curation decisions are listed in the Curation View (top left).

Figure 5: An example `SpikeInterface-GUI` window, showing Views with external user data. Here, the user has created a custom view using the plugin system which plots the rate map of a unit in a 2D open arena. This experiment also involved optogenetics stimulation and we plot the raster plot of all stimulation events (bottom left). This Figure shows that `SpikeInterface-GUI` can be used to compare behavioral data, user-provided events, raw ephys data and spike sorter output. In this Figure, the user has entered “Focus mode” by pressing `ctrl + f`, hiding the settings options for each View.

this case, the user can “split” the unit into two by lasso-selecting individual spikes in any of the scatter Views (e.g., spike amplitudes, spike depths).

There is much customization built into the GUI including a plugin system which allows users to add their own custom views. The main use case is for bespoke Views which display behavioral data in a task. We show such an example in Figure 5, where the user has created a view displaying an open field rate map including the position of the subject (blue cross) at the time of the selected spike. The Figure also shows the Event View, which can generate event-aligned raster and peri-stimulus time histograms (PSTH) plots. Overall, this layout combines synchronized data from raw ephys, spike sorter output, events (e.g. optogenetics stimulation) and behavior.

Availability and future directions

In this paper we have introduced `SpikeInterface-GUI`, a visualization tool for spike sorting output. We have demonstrated that the tool can be used for a variety of applications: assessing spike sorting outputs alongside raw data, quality curation, assessing merges and splits, and viewing behavioral data for a bespoke experiment using the plugin system. We hope the GUI will simplify and speed up the spike sorting workflow in labs of all scales, while ensuring provenance of human curation decisions. We note that the implementation of the GUI is only possible due to significant developments in `SpikeInterface`: primarily the development of the `SortingAnalyzer` and the `Curation` format. We also hope the GUI will help algorithm developers by giving them fast feedback on the results of their methods.

The codebase is designed to be maintainable and extensible, with a View being particularly easy to create and modify. The central Controller, which handles data retrieval and signaling, is carefully optimized to ensure a fast user-experience, even when viewing terabyte-scale raw

data.

In the future, we plan to continue supporting algorithms implemented in `SpikeInterface`, especially auto-merging and auto-splitting tools. We hope external users will contribute new Views to the package and find additional use-cases for the GUI.

One avenue for future work relies on the web backend. When `SpikeInterface-GUI` is run on a web server, with access to a variety of analyzers stored in the cloud, users can view and interact with this data from anywhere in the world. This setup allows for community based projects. For instance, researchers could curate a set of units, and this data can then be used to train models to automatically identify “good” units. Such a project has recently been done on a small scale [13], but `SpikeInterface-GUI` allows for global-scale spike sorting curation.

The code and documentation for `SpikeInterface-GUI` is available on GitHub, at <https://github.com/SpikeInterface/spikeinterface-gui/>. The package can be installed into any Python environment using `pip` or `uv` and there are installation instructions in the GitHub repository linked above.

The `SpikeInterface` Project manages the `SpikeInterface-GUI` codebase. The core package, `SpikeInterface`, is under active development with a large user base. There have been 116 contributors¹ and it has received 764 stars on GitHub, half of which were earned in the past two years. We believe it is the most widely used software in electrophysiology and the team has a proven track record of developing long-lasting, high-impact tools. The `SpikeInterface-GUI` package is built atop a vibrant community which will ensure the software remains resilient, updated and responsive to the evolving needs of its users.

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